

PROFESSIONAL BURNOUT AND ITS PREVENTION IN INTERNAL AFFAIRS OFFICERS

Abu Rayhan Beruni
Urgench State University
Independent researcher
Bogbekova Dilnoza Shonazarovna

Abstract: *This thesis examines the psychological mechanisms, main indicators, and preventive measures of professional burnout in internal affairs officers. Professional burnout is associated with the depletion of an individual's emotional and energy resources resulting from constant stress and high psychological pressure. The study analyzes the main components of the syndrome, such as emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced job satisfaction. Additionally, the importance of effective rest, developing positive communication skills, pursuing personal growth, self-management, and proper delegation of responsibilities in preventing burnout is scientifically substantiated.*

Keywords: *professional burnout, stress, internal affairs body, emotional exhaustion, psychological defense, prevention, rest, stress resilience, motivation, communication skills, personal growth, professional stability.*

Professional burnout syndrome develops against a backdrop of constant stress. It leads to the depletion of the employee's personal and emotional-energy resources. This problem arises from the inability to find an outlet for accumulated negative emotions.

The term "burnout" was first used in 1974 by psychiatrist H. Freudenberger[4]. He studied the condition of mentally healthy individuals who received psychological services based on their type of activity.

Since then, burnout has been studied and diagnosed in people of various professions and ages, confirming that any person, regardless of gender, age, and type of activity, is susceptible to "burnout."

Often, the "victims" of professional fatigue are people whose profession involves communication with a large number of individuals: managers, sales representatives, medical and social workers, consultants, teachers, police officers, journalists.

The next candidates for professional fatigue are people who fear losing their job for objective reasons: those approaching retirement age, those lacking good

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qualifications, and those who lack confidence in their professional skills. Additionally, the risk group includes

"free creators," those who seek work independently - freelancers, independent managers.

Three main symptoms of emotional fatigue syndrome are identified [1]:

1. "Emotional and/or physical fatigue"

Emotional fatigue manifests as a feeling of overexertion and exhaustion, the depletion of one's emotional resources, and a persistent feeling of tiredness even after a night's sleep. After a rest period (days off, vacation), these manifestations decrease, but reappear when returning to the previous work routine.

2. "Personal isolation"

This symptom is characterized by a person beginning to perceive their thoughts, feelings, and even actions as alienated, without internal involvement. The work process becomes impersonal and formal. A person is shielded from any experiences, including the protective mechanism for conserving strength and energy reserves, by an invisible screen.

3. Work-related "self-dissatisfaction."

If successes at work no longer inspire, then one can speak about the presence of this sign[2].

Below, we will examine in detail the symptoms that arise from professional burnout at work:

Psychophysical symptoms:

- chronic fatigue syndrome - feeling tired even after waking up in the morning;
- feeling of emotional and physical exhaustion;
- general weakness, which can be diagnosed even through biochemical blood test indicators;
- headaches and digestive disorders;
- weight-related problems (rapid weight loss or weight gain);
- sleep problems;
- decreased vision, hearing, smell, and touch during physical exertion, shortness of breath, or breathing difficulties.

Socio-psychological symptoms:

- decreased vitality, low mood, depression;
- high irritability, unexplained outbursts of anger;
- constantly experiencing negative emotions, feeling upset, being suspicious;
- inner anticipation of unpleasantness, readiness for life's troubles;

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- fear of failure, lack of self-confidence.

Behavioral signs:

- feeling that work you once loved is becoming increasingly unpleasant and burdensome;
- changing work patterns;
- the employee always takes work home, but doesn't complete it there;
- decreased enthusiasm for work, a feeling that the work being performed is futile;
- unwillingness to communicate with the team, heightened criticism towards colleagues and superiors (or subordinates);
- excessive alcohol consumption, increasing the number of cigarettes smoked during the day, use of narcotic drugs or medications.

If you discover that you're at risk of professional burnout, or even notice its first signs in yourself, no one is immune to losing interest in work they once enjoyed. However, how can you protect yourself from professional burnout?

What should be done if the problem is already evident and simple prevention of occupational fatigue no longer helps?

- The most crucial and important thing - never forget to rest!

Anyone who works hard and efficiently is familiar with these thoughts: "I'll work for another hour or two and go to bed later," "Instead of a break, I'd better tidy up my desk," "How can I take a vacation with so much work!"

Thus, stress, strain, and fatigue accumulate. Therefore, it is advisable to start all recovery procedures with a vacation. Moreover, it should be conducted according to a comprehensive program: it should last at least two weeks and include a change of scenery, delicious meals, various attractions, the sea, and the sun. Incidentally, sunlight is very important for health.

- Changes in the work environment

The easiest way to make a change is to propose switching places with a colleague.

Establish cleanliness: throw away trash, get rid of old papers and unnecessary items. Put the remaining things in their proper places and organize the folders. After putting things in order, try to give your workplace a personal touch: place your favorite items and photos on the desk, add a few bright accents, and liven up the room with a houseplant.

- Pursue education

In addition to combating professional fatigue, you will simultaneously achieve another goal - improving your skills. Consider which direction you want to develop in. What knowledge and skills do you lack to perform successfully?

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- Introduce interest and variety into your life outside of work

First, engage in sports. Scientists have proven that sport helps elevate mood and reduce stress levels due to the production of "happiness hormones."

Secondly, find a hobby. Engaging in an activity that interests you and has nothing to do with work will be very beneficial for you - you'll realize that work is not the only meaning in life, you'll be distracted from it, and you'll simply relax and enjoy yourself.

- Delegating Authority

Transferring one's rights and responsibilities to others can be very important and beneficial.

To make your work as effective as possible, it's necessary to remember several rules when delegating authority. Firstly, you always delegate authority not to a specific person, but to the position they hold. Secondly, the transferred rights and responsibilities must be sufficient to achieve the expected results in increasing the overall effectiveness of the team's work. Thirdly, it is advisable that all subordinates report to one boss, not to several. Fourthly, decisions within the competence of individual managers should be made by them, not passed on to others.

- upwards. Fifthly, the boss is responsible for leading subordinates, while subordinates are responsible for the work they do[3].

- Improve communication skills The main risk factor for professional burnout is excessive interaction with a large number of people. Many negative experiences arise from a person's inability to say "no." Usually, people who don't say no to anyone can't set priorities - everything seems important to them. And almost everyone They get upset because of rejections.

Divide all incoming requests into those that need to be fulfilled, those that can be fulfilled, those that can be postponed, and those that need to be rejected.

- Take advantage of personal growth

Psychologists describe a number of qualities, the presence of which significantly reduces the likelihood of developing occupational burnout syndrome.

These include self-confidence and confidence in one's abilities, high self-esteem, the ability to adapt to difficult working conditions, stress resistance, experience in successfully overcoming stress, openness, sociability, independence, high adaptability, positive thinking, and optimism.

- Talk to your manager

Describe to them what you are tired of, what exhausts and irritates you. Suggest ways to improve the situation, for example, modifying the job description or transferring to another position. A competent leader can appreciate your initiative, honesty, and desire

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to benefit the organization. It is in the company's best interests to support you and find all opportunities for you to demonstrate your abilities and talents, as well as to contribute to the company's activities.

– Change jobs

The most radical and at the same time effective means against occupational burnout. No old job - no old problems.

Other basic preventive actions include:

1. Choose a job you enjoy.
2. Love yourself, or at the very least, treat yourself with kindness and care.
3. Do not seek salvation or happiness solely from work.
4. Allocate time not only for work but also for your personal needs.

Thus, burnout resulting from occupational stress occurs when a person's adaptive capabilities (resources) for overcoming stressful situations are exceeded.

Signs of burnout include: decreased work motivation, a sharp increase in job dissatisfaction, workplace conflicts, chronic fatigue, boredom, exhaustion, irritability, anxiety, detachment from the workplace, colleagues, tardiness, increased absenteeism, and others.

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